

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ICT IN EDUCATION INDICATORS.

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article describes conceptual framework of ICT in educational sphere. With the use of computers in education, ICT was expected to lead to more productive learning. Yet, early studies on the impact of ICT on educational outcomes did not produce very consistent results. The overall conclusion of the authors is that research has identified positive effects of specific ICT uses on pupil's educational attainment. The most substantial effects were observed when ICT was used in mathematics, science and English.

Keywords: evolution, information requirements, policy monitoring, national education systems, pedagogical vision and competence, computer skills, policy implementation, education framework, quality-assured digital educational, policymakers, monitoring and evaluation.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной научной статье описываются концептуальные основы использования ИКТ в образовательной сфере. Ожидалось, что использование компьютеров в образовании приведет к более продуктивному обучению. Тем не менее, ранние исследования влияния ИКТ на результаты образования не дали очень последовательных результатов. Общий вывод авторов заключается в том, что исследования выявили положительное влияние конкретных видов использования ИКТ на образовательные достижения учащихся. Наиболее существенные эффекты наблюдались при использовании ИКТ в математике, естественных науках и английском языке.

Ключевые слова: эволюция, информационные потребности, мониторинг политики, национальные системы образования, педагогическое видение и компетентность, компьютерные навыки, реализация политики, структура

образования, цифровое образование гарантированного качества, политики, мониторинг и оценка.

Introduction. Since the introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT), their integration into education and the associated financial investments have been policy concerns in many countries. The initiatives that were taken to give ICT a place in education have resulted in a need to monitor these developments, using reliable and valid indicators. Once these indicators are available through standardized international data collection efforts, policymakers can review progress of their countries over time in comparison with their nationally defined targets and other relevant reference countries.

Countries that are in the early stages of introducing ICT have different information needs from countries that have longer experience with the technology. For instance, when introducing computers in education, it is important that teachers and students have access to hardware and software and that they acquire basic computer skills. Countries in more advanced stages of ICT use in education have other priorities come to the forefront – such as the management of pedagogical innovation, adaptive and inclusive curriculum, organizational change, sustainable technical support, and continued staff development. As a result, the concerns of policymakers have shifted over time. For some, measuring the impact of the implementation of ICT in education entails information on access, use, and outcomes. For others, in the early days of implementation, the focus is on creating an ICT infrastructure in order to provide schools with access to newer technologies. The subsequent focus is on using ICT in an appropriate way in order to realize intended educational outcomes.

Methodology

In order to monitor ICT in education from an international perspective, it is necessary to establish a consensus on the conceptual framework first. However, some operational constraints must be considered as well. The UIS approach emphasizes educational institutions (or schools) as the main units of data collection, aggregated at the country level. This method of data collection has important consequences for the framework for monitoring access to, use and outcomes of ICT in education. For example, some indicators of interest – such as ICT use by teachers and students (at schools and/or at home) and the impact of ICT on student competencies – cannot be directly measured through such methods. Moreover, it is important to note that countries are at different stages of introducing technology (in various forms) in

schools. **Figure 1** illustrates the evolution of information needs with the stages of nationwide implementation of cross-sectoral ICT policies and with the changing levels of ICT penetration in educational systems over time. As ICT permeates education systems, the indicators that are used for monitoring progress in policy implementation change over time. An international instrument that collects administrative data across numerous countries at different stages of development and implementation must be sensitive to such situations. However, as countries reach the later stages of information requirements (e.g. e-impact) and where resources allow, monitoring the impact of ICT can be more effectively achieved through sample-based assessments, labour force surveys and other specialized longitudinal surveys.

The literature on ICT in education covers many conceptual frameworks. **Figure 2** provides an example of a common framework for ICT in education. It provides a useful basis for upstream policy monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. Law et al. (2008) and Pelgrum and Anderson (1999) have noted that SITES 2006 was based on the concept that using ICT forms part of the pedagogical practices of the teacher: "For teachers, the reasons for and the ways of using ICT in the classroom are underpinned by their overall pedagogical vision and competence. Also, pedagogical practices are not determined solely by the characteristics of the teachers, such as their academic qualifications and ICT-competence, but also by school and system level factors. While we expect students' learning outcomes to be influenced by the pedagogical practices they experience, we need to acknowledge that the outcomes (whether perceived or actual) influence the subsequent pedagogical decisions of the teacher. This is because teacher-, school- and system-level factors often have to change or be changed to accommodate the expected or actual impact of pedagogical practices on students."

Figure 1. Information needs at different levels of ICT penetration in education systems over time

Figure 2. Conceptual framework

From an operational perspective, a classic approach to an ICT in education framework comprises “policy / strategy-input-process-output / outcomes”. **Figure 3** illustrates the practical nature of the relationships between key areas.

Figure 3. Operational and conceptual framework for ICT integration in education

Conclusion.In summary, before ICT integration into national education systems can be effective, an adequate mix of the following policy and operational measures is needed:

i) Clear goals and a policy environment enabled by national authorities that support the use of ICT in education;

ii) Support and/or incentives for both public and private educational institutions to purchase ICT facilities (e.g. dedicated government funding, including a budget for maintenance services; tax rebates on ICT hardware and software for educational institutions; investment in or sponsoring of research in developing low-cost ICT hardware and software, etc);

iii) Adaptation of curricula to ICT integration and development or acquisition of standardized quality-assured digital educational contents and software;

iv) Deliberate mass teacher training programmes on teaching ICT subjects or using ICT to teach other subjects more effectively;

v) Favourable and flexible school policies enabling well-planned access by teachers and learners to ICT resources in support of curricula delivery; and

vi) Appropriate national-level monitoring and evaluation systems that make it possible to perform regular assessments of outcomes and efficiency gains, and to detect early potential shortcomings so that policy implementation can be more effective.

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